

A Study on the Impact of Digitalization on Customers in Banking Sector with Regard to ICICI Bank - Bengaluru

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Dr. K. Ashwini

*Associate Professor & Co-ordinator, Department of Post Graduate Studies
Jain College, Bangalore*

S. Ramya & G. Pooja

Students, Jain College, Vasavi Temple Road, V.V Puram, Bengaluru

Abstract

Banking sector being the backbone of the economy has a very vital role to play for the development of a country. Digitalization on the other hand has become indispensable for the development of all the sectors globally, even more important in the banking sector. This paper studies on the impact of digitalization on customers and the paper studies the customer satisfaction of private banks, in specific ICICI bank. The study reveals that security concern and internet access is the main drawback of online banking. Majority of them use online banking as it saves time and quick transactions, 24hours of availability. Online banking helps for any bill payments, transfer money between accounts, and one can check balances wherever they are. To conclude it is the bank's responsibility to create awareness about online banking services in rural areas and educate the people by personally explaining to them the online process.

Keywords: Digitalization, Security Concern, Online Banking.

Introduction

Banking- A Global Scenario

As long as the civilization has come into existence, the banking have also been existed. Before civilization existed, there were bank-like system. The proper banks have come into existence in ancient Mesopotamia. In Babylonia and other cities they have provided lending activities. All these is not in the form of financial lending. Instead, they would lend out seeds and the like.

Modern banking in India originated in the last decade of the 18th century. The word ‘bank’ is used in the commercial bank. It is also originated from French word ‘Banqui’ and Italian word ‘Banca’ which is referred to a bench for keeping, lending and exchanging of money or coins in the market place by money lenders and money changers.

The first bank in India was the ‘Bank of Hindustan’ started in 1770 by Alexander and company.

In the history it was called as ‘merchant banking’ which means trading on commodities. In India such merchant’s bankers were known as ‘Seths’.

The next stage is Goldsmith. The business of goldsmith was that he had to take special precautions against theft of gold and jewelry. As this practice continued, the goldsmith started charging something for taking care of money or gold.

The later which came into existence was moneylender. The goldsmith found that withdrawals of coins were much less than the deposits with him. So he started advancing the coins on loan by charging interest.

Then came mergers and acquisition which started its presence from 1800s, and it had become admired trend throughout the country. And its main motive in banking sector is to harvest the benefit of economies of scales.

RBI

Reserve bank of India was established in 1934 following the Reserve Bank India act and it was nationalized in 1949. RBI was founded on 1st April 1935 to respond to economic troubles after the 1st World War. In 1949, the banking regulation act was enacted, which empowered the Reserve Bank of India to regulate, control and inspect the bank in India. RBI is India’s Central Bank, which controls the assurance and supply of the Indian rupee. Its main function is to regulate the issue of Bank Notes and keeping of reserve with a view to securing monetary stability in India and generally to operate the currency and credit system of the country to its advantage.

The banks were asked to push funds towards sectors that the Government wanted to target for growth. Indira Gandhi told the Lok sabha that the “the purpose of nationalization is to promote rapid growth in agriculture, small industries and exports, to encourage new entrepreneurs and to develop all backward areas”.

Kinds of banks in India

There are 2 broad categories under which banks are classified in India, they are:

1. Scheduled banks
2. Non-scheduled banks

Scheduled banks/ nationalized banks: They are the banks which are covered under the 2nd schedule of reserve bank of Indian act 1935. This includes commercial and cooperation banks. They are

1. SBI-5 associate lenders like Jaipur, Travancore, Patiala, Mysore and Hyderabad
2. Punjab national bank- Oriental bank of commerce- United bank
3. Canara bank- Syndicate bank
4. Union bank of India- Andhra bank- corporation bank
5. Indian bank- Allahabad bank

Non-scheduled banks/ private banks: They are the banks which are not listed in the 2nd schedule of Reserve Bank of Indian Act 1935. These are the banks which provide healthy competition on general efficiency levels in banking system. They offer high degree of professional management, creates healthy competition and encourages foreign investment. Some of the private banks are:

1. ICICI Bank
2. Axis Bank
3. HDFC Bank
4. Kotak Mahindra Bank
5. YES Bank
6. IndusInd Bank

7. IDFC Bank
8. Bandhan Bank

ICICI Bank: It is an Indian multinational banking and financial services company headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra with its registered office in Vadodara, Gujarat and it is 2nd largest bank in India in terms of assets and market capitalization. It was established by the Industrial Credit and Interest Corporation of India (ICICI). It was founded on 5th January 1994, 25 years ago and it started its Internet banking operations in 1998. As on March 31st 2018, the bank has a network of 4867 branches and 14367 ATMs across India and has a presence in 17 countries including India. ICICI Bank is one of the big four banks of India.

Digitalization of Banks

The earliest forms of digital banking trace back to the advent of ATMs and cards launched in 1960s as the internet emerged in the 1980s with early broadband digital networks began to connect retailers with suppliers and consumers to develop needs for early online catalogues and inventory software systems. By the 1990s the internet became widely available and online banking started becoming the norm. The online banking and telebanking made their appearance in the 2000s.

The reason digital banking is more than just a mobile or online platform is that it includes middleware solutions. Middleware is software that bridges operating systems or databases with other applications. It is a form of banking in which funds are transferred through an exchange of electronic signals than through an exchange of cash, cheques or other types of documents. It allows users to conduct financial transactions through the internet. They also do all the services like deposits, transfers, online bill payments. The nature of online banking is as follows:

1. It pays bills online- online bill payment is a secure electronic service that allows customers to pay bills without having to write cheques and mail them.
2. View your transactions- it helps to view all our account transactions details through internet without going to bank.
3. Transfer money between accounts- online banking allows you to transfer accounts much more quickly and check on your available funds before spending money.
4. Mobile banking- most banks will have a mobile app that allows you to take advantage of online banking on your phone.
5. Reports check- through online banking we can check our bank statements where ever we are.
6. SMS banking services- online banking provides our account balances and any information about the facilities available through SMS.

Set back of digitalization

Absence of face to face interactions which make it very impersonal. Lack of trust on online services. Difficult mode of services for the first timers. It involves security risk. If the banks server is down, customers can't use it.

Future of Digitalization

Through internet banking customer can operate his account while sitting in office or home. Customers can withdraw at any time through ATMs which are now widely available throughout the country. It also helped in payment of electricity, telephone bill and mobile recharge. The growth of credit card usage is wide. Now a customer need not carry paper money with him. It will be available 24/7. It also lower the cost of entry. It has also increased the transparency. It makes anytime access to accounts and loan information possible.

Review of Literature

The research papers which is already done by the previous researcher was studied which highlights on This paper studies on the different banks is on condition that e-banking services, as this revolutionize their profits. The paper concludes that it is essential for e-banking institutions to enhance the usage of internet as a banking channel by their customers. It has also made an attempt to look into the factors that drives and inhibits internet banking usage in India. Ankit Kesharwani and Gajulapally Radhakrishna (2013),

Rakesh H M and Ramya T J (2014) titled “A Study on Factors Influencing Consumer Adoption of Internet Banking in India” tried to examine the factors that influence internet banking adoption. They successfully proved and found that internet banking is influenced by its perceived reliability, Perceived ease of use and Perceived usefulness

Donnelie K Muzividzi, Rangarirai Mbizi and Tinashe Mukwazhe(2013) In their research paper “An Analysis of Factors that influence internet banking adoption among Intellectuals: Case of Chinhoyi University of Technology”. This paper investigates the adoption on internet banking has remained sluggish despite the efforts by banks to promote the technology. The purpose of the research project was to identify the factors that affect the adoption of internet banking in a bid to construct ways to salvage the situation. The research focused on intellectuals who better understand technology than the general public. The results revealed that adopters and non-adopters realized that internet banking has a quite lot of benefits and amenities. The non-adopters were concerned about factors such as trust, ease of use, awareness and security. The results also showed the adopters had a positive influence on use of online banking and experience in using online banking.

Shilpi Khandelwal (2013) In his research titled on “E-Banking: Factors of Adoption in India” This paper presents the last decade has witnessed a drastic change in the economic and banking environment all over the world. Internet banking has brought about a 360-degree change in the entire banking industry. The wider usage of cell phone and internet certainly seems to be playing a role of blurring physical boundaries and unlocking a whole world of opportunities for banks for tapping newer customer segments and in recording greater volume of transactions. This research paper is focused on what are the drivers that drive consumers towards adoption of E-banking.

Set Back of igitalization

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Statement of Problem

Banks have provided more effective and easy online banking facility to the customers, but still this facility is not affected by most of the customer. The main problem associated with online banking services are the security concerns and therefore, this study has been undertaken to know the pros and cons of online banking and to bridge a gap between the urban consumer and rural consumer.

Objective of the Study

1. To create awareness for the customer towards e-banking facilities.
2. To understand the problems of e-banking.
3. To know the challenges faced by customers in electronic banking.

Limitations of the Study

1. Lack of time
2. Limited resources
3. Banks have a vast study
4. Time consuming
5. Financial constraints

Research Methodology

- Sampling method: Convenient method
- Sample size: 60 respondents
- Data: Primary data
- Sampling technique: Questionnaire

It comprises of a detailed study of the problems and prospects of online banking services and level of customer satisfaction by the internet banking. The primary data so collected is from 60 respondents, who have replied on factors like age, gender, occupation, annual income, types of account and so on.

Results

- From the study we can see that all the respondents majorly use savings bank account. It further seen that all the respondents are using savings account compared to current account because most of the respondents are students, private sectors who use online banking frequently.
- It can be concluded that majority of the respondents comes under below 100000 annual income category which portray below poverty line.
- There are many respondents who agrees that manual banking is more convenient than online banking because of the security concerns.
- It can be seen that majority of the respondents opt for ATM services and mobile banking because majority of the respondents are students and employees who wants fast transactions to take place and also to saves time. Less number of respondents use phone banking because of poor network connections.
- It can be further seen that majority of the respondents use online fund transfer because it saves time and can be operated 24/7. We can also see many respondents use online banking to check the balances because the respondents are getting salaries, scholarships, subsidies to their account. So they use frequently to confirm that the amount in their account is secured.
- Further we can see majority of the respondent’s use online banking on a weekly and a monthly basis because they make other bill payments, for shopping and so on. Nowadays respondents are more familiar to mobile apps such as google pay, paytm, phonepe etc to make their daily payments.
- Further it can clearly says that online banking is largely accepted as it saves time and efforts of the respondents who opt for online banking services.
- From the study we can observe that 3.3% says that human contact for banking relation is not at all required, 45% agrees that human contact is required but 51.7% of respondents says that it might be required or may not. Further we can conclude that majority are in a confusion as to human contact for banking relation is required or not because some believe that human presence should be there to check out whether all transactions are done correctly and some believe in that everything done online may be in perfection.
- Further we can conclude that majority of respondents visit their bank less often because of their lack of time they do most of their transactions in online banking only but 48.3% of respondents visit their bank even after having online banking because they believe that online banking has

lack of security and some fraud activities might take place.

- It can be further we can conclude that majority of respondents are unsatisfied with the online banking services because it has lack of security problem which affects the feeling of the customers to transact in online banking.

Chart showing the awareness of the respondents about online banking

Aware of online banking
60 responses

From the study we can notice that 93.3% of the respondents are aware of online banking services and 6.7% of respondents are not aware of it. Further we can see that majority of the respondents are aware of online banking services provided by ICICI Bank. But few people who are not aware of it, its bank responsibility to reach all the customers and make aware of it.

Source: Primary Data

Chart showing the trust on security in online banking services

From the study we can analyze that 71.7% of respondents have less trust on the security of online banking. 25% of respondents completely trust on security of online banking and 3.3% of respondents are in a confusion whether to trust online banking or not. Further we can interpret that majority of respondents have less trust on the security of online banking they might have the feeling that some fraud things might occur in online transactions. About 25% of respondents completely trust the security in online banking and least number of respondents are unsure whether to trust online banking or not because of security problem.

Do you trust the security of online banking services
60 responses

Source: Primary Data

Chart showing preference of banking system

It is analyzed from the study that 76.7% of respondents use mobile banking whereas 15% of respondent's use internet banking and only 8.3% of respondents use conventional banking. From the above chart, it can be interpreted that most of respondents use mobile banking which allows respondents to carry out their transaction where ever they are by not visiting the bank for any purpose whereas some percentage of respondents use internet banking due to security problem and the least percentage of respondents use conventional banking because it requires human presence at bank for every transaction.

What do you prefer the most
60 responses

Source: Primary Data

Chart showing main reasons of drawbacks of internet banking

It is analyzed that, 55% of respondents feel security concern is the drawback in internet banking. 13.3% feels that lack of internet access and limited services as the drawback whereas 16.7% feels that lack of face to face advices is not there and 1.7% feels critical process as the drawback. From the above chart, we can conclude that majority of respondent’s feels that security concern is the main reason of drawback which is lacking in internet banking as it includes most of the fraudulent activities like ATM card frauds, hacking and so on.

main reasons of drawbacks of Internet banking
60 responses

Source: Primary Data

Chart showing reasons for satisfaction towards the online banking services

It is analyzed that, 51.7% feels satisfied because of 24 hours of availability. 26.7% feels that it saves time whereas 10% feels that there is fast transactions and no need to visit bank often. Only 1.6% feels it is cheap and best. From the above chart, we can interpret that majority of respondents were satisfied with online banking because it is available 24/7 and respondents can operate their account anytime and at anywhere they are.

Mention your reason for satisfaction towards the online banking services
60 responses

Source: Primary Data

Chart showing overall opinion about online banking

From the above table, we can analyze that 63.3% tells that online banking services are good. 31.7% comments excellent but only 5% gives average result. We can conclude that majority of respondents have good opinion about online banking services because it has more benefits which are useful to all customers.

What is your overall opinion about online banking
60 responses

Source: Primary Data

Conclusion

The data we collected, can see many people are aware of online banking services. They are satisfied with online banking services because of fast transactions and 24hours availability. Due to all these factors customers of the ICICI bank are accepting internet banking. The bank have provided various services to the customers but that is not thoroughly used by them due to various hurdles like security concern, internet access etc. So, banks should take a precautionary measures through awareness campaigns, educating people and providing more meaningful advertisements to

make online banking popular to all the age group. The bank also has to create confidence and trust in minds of the customers towards the security of the accounts.

Suggestions

1. They need to create trust and confident among the customer towards the security of their accounts.
2. To educate people who are not aware of online banking services.
3. Proper training to customers for using online banking services.
4. To make sites more user friendly.
5. The bank has to provide advertisements in rural areas, so that it spreads awareness in the minds of people about online banking services.
6. If we want to have a cashless economy in India it's our duty to know much about online banking services.
7. Through the usage of online banking services the flow of black money and corruption will reduce in the economy.

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